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MODERN PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS AND THEIR TARGET ORIENTATION.**Pan Olga Afanasyevna**Senior Lecturer at the Kimyo
International University in Tashkent

Abstract. Russian Phraseology The article considers the question of teaching phraseology to students while improving the Russian language, emphasizes the need to study phraseological units at an advanced stage, when students already have a sufficient vocabulary and generally have a good command of the grammar of the Russian language. Attention is focused on the fact that the successful assimilation of phraseological units by students requires purposeful work and careful selection of language material.

Keywords: phraseological units, phraseology of the Russian language, origin of phraseological units, methods of teaching phraseology, competence.

The history of phraseology as a linguistic discipline of Russian linguistics goes back to the works of M. V. Lomonosov, who believed that "phrases" and "idioms" must necessarily be presented in the dictionary. He was engaged in research on the "living language" and collected a very large number of proverbs of the Russian language. Phraseology emerged as an independent linguistic discipline in the 40s of the XX century. It is then that scientists are faced with the question of the meaning of stable expressions in different languages. In the future, theories related to the description of phraseological units as structural units of the language are being developed, attempts are being made to describe phraseological units in dictionaries, for example, in the work of A. I. Molotkov "Phraseological Dictionary of the Russian language". [1]

V. V. Vinogradov made a huge contribution to the study of phraseology, it was he who raised questions about its basic concepts, scope and tasks, in the future his ideas were continued and developed in the works of A. I. Molotkov, V. P. Zhukov, V. N. Telii.

Phraseologism, or phraseological unit - stable in composition and structure, lexically indivisible and integral in meaning, a phrase or sentence that performs the function of a separate lexeme.

Phraseological units, phraseological turns or phrasemes - "these are stable figurative turns that are perceived in speech like a word, and are not created in the process of communication or writing a text." As a science of language, it contributes to the formation of an active linguistic personality in the conditions of the modern linguistic situation. Russian language teaching lexico-phraseological and linguistic-cultural aspects, the formation of competence in the field of Russian national mentality and culture are important directions in the modern didactics of teaching the Russian language. [1]

Russian phraseology, speech etiquette, rituals and traditions is therefore a necessary and most demanded task, the solution of which contributes to the formation of Russian

language identity, strengthens the role of the Russian language as a means of uniting the nation, is an significant component in the formation of the communicative competence of students studying Russian.

Phraseological units reflect the national culture in a complex way, with all their idiomatic meaning, as well as their prototypes, since free phrases that became phraseological described certain customs, traditions, details of everyday life and culture, historical events and much more. Phraseology as a section contains a huge educational, developmental and educational potential. [2]

"Phraseology is understood as a stable and reproducible differently formed unit of language, consisting of components, endowed with a holistic meaning and combined with other words. Phraseology begins where the semantic realization of its components ends."

Phraseological units carry cultural information about the world, society, and act as a means of characterization of a linguistic personality. Modern slang phraseological units, depending on the method of transformation, can be divided into the following groups:

1) - units formed by replacing the vocabulary components of the motivating phraseological turnover, with a radical change in their denotative and connotative meaning, creating a rough, reduced expressiveness:

- for example: not hello - about a misunderstanding of something and about a situation in which there is awkwardness, tension, something unsaid ... not a potato - not a trifle at all; not so simple; about something quite complex, significant;

- to gain courage - to become impudent, impudent ... to gain intelligence (reason) - to become smart, to get smarter, to gain strength, to get health, to gain strength, health;

2) - units formed by replacing the vocabulary components of the motivating phraseological turnover and retaining the original meaning, for example: raise the vocal - raise the voice, expressing dissatisfaction with someone, something ... raise the voice - speak louder than usual, with irritation;

- to get into a can -to find yourself in a difficult, unpleasant situation, to get into trouble ... to get into a bind -to find yourself in a difficult, difficult, dangerous or unpleasant situation;

3) - stable combinations formed by rethinking their internal form, when semantic associations are established between the components of phraseology and words of free use that coincide in sound: for example, a rethought internal form of a phrase

- being on a diet manifests itself in the meaning of "temporarily stop using obscene expressions" and is based on the presence of a common theme to temporarily stop using something.

In student jargon, you can find a joking expression homework, which means "part of the treat, taken with you from a banquet, a party." In this case, a direct derivational relationship is established between the direct meaning of the adjective home and the slang lexico-semantic variant, which consists in the presence of a common feature related to home;

4) - phraseological units formed by borrowing terms and professional words that acquire a new meaning, expressive coloring in youth jargon and lose their accuracy and stylistic neutrality: for example, in the musical and computer spheres: to get behind the sharps - "to get into the conclusion" (from the name of a musical sign resembling a lattice). [11]

The main task to be solved when teaching the Russian language is to ensure that the processes of acquiring knowledge about the structure and functioning of the native language, mastering the basic norms of the modern Russian literary language, forming the ability to use its richest stylistic resources are organically combined with the intensive development of speech-thinking, intellectual, creative abilities. [12]

In addition, the study of phraseological units should be accompanied by their use in speech, interpretation of the meaning of phraseological phrases and their appropriate use in conversation. The main goal is to give an idea of phraseology as a linguistic unit.

The following tasks follow from the set goal:

- 1) show the similarity and difference with the word and phrase;
- 2) show the specifics of the meaning of phraseology in comparison with a free phrase;
- 3) give an idea of systemic relations in phraseology (synonymy, antonym);
- 4) give the concept of phraseological dictionaries.

Examples from modern phraseological units:

- o To precipitate (to be shocked by the actions or words of another person)
- o To vote with your feet (to leave or not to come to a meeting, elections, etc.)
- o To hammer a bolt (not to pay attention)
- o Captain obviousness (about a person abusing platitudes)
- o To cover a clearing (to throw a banquet, how to celebrate some event with invitees)
- o Not in the stream (not suitable, inappropriate)
- o No need to la-la (no need to talk your teeth, chat)
- o Office plankton (typical office employee, not distinguished by high productivity)
- o Orthodoxy of the brain (about the inflexible orthodox approach of a person to any life issue)
- o Light at the end of the tunnel (the appearance of hope for a way out of a difficult situation) [3]

One of the main features of phraseological units is that words cannot be arbitrarily replaced in them, i.e. they have a constant lexical composition. This feature distinguishes phraseological units from free phrases.

This can be confirmed, for example, by the fact that such expressions use words that are not clear to everyone. They say, for example, to get into a mess, although not everyone knows what a mess is; or to sharpen mistakes, to set a run, although not everyone knows what aslip or arun is. (The word vprsak came from the words in and prosak - that was the name of the camp for twisting ropes. Hence the meaning of the expression: it was very unpleasant to get into such a camp with hair. The word lyasi (balusters) meant "chiseled posts to support the railing." The origin of this expression is

associated with the light and cheerful profession of people who grind these columns, lovers of talking, chatting while working. The word *strekach* meant "flight".)[4]

Phraseological units are characterized by emotional expressiveness. They not only name the phenomena of reality (they are called through comparison, figuratively), but also convey the speaker's attitude to the named phenomenon. Emotionality and imagery of phraseological units are not always noticed by speakers, but the comparison of phraseological units with words and phrases enlivens their emotionality and imagery. [5]

Due to the figurative nature of phraseological units, they perform an expressive function, they bring imagery to texts, make speech more expressive. It is no accident that writers and journalists see in Russian phraseology excellent examples of figurative expression of the phenomena of reality and use them in their professional activities. Thus, phraseological units can be used in the headlines of articles and essays in the media: "Sticks in the wheels of the Automotive Industry", "How not to "lose your head?" ("Arguments and Facts", No. 4, 2020), "How to make a movie without a penny in your pocket" ("Khakassia", No. 241-242, 2019), "And took his own life" ("Khakassia", No. 211-212, 2019) "And so that the mosquito did not undermine his nose" ("Khakassia", No. 183-184, 2019), the subtitle "Everything got away with it" to the article "Such and such escaped from the palace" ("Komsomolskaya Pravda" from January 15-22, 2020). There are also various methods of using phraseological phrases in articles and essays: "... And then it's time to separate the wheat from the chaff..." (Yu. Abumov in the article "Repetition is the mother of learning" ("Khakassia", No. 244-245, 2019), "... He caught fire with the idea, and a few days later he called and said, that the script is ready!" (M. Bankova in the article "How to make a movie without a penny in your pocket" ("Khakassia", No. 241-242, 2019). [6]

Phraseological units of the literary language existing in oral and written form are used in different ways in different spheres of its application - in everyday communication of people with each other, in official business relations of citizens with institutions and institutions with citizens, in journalism, science and in verbal and artistic creativity.

A certain part of phraseological units performs the functions of generalization and expressive function, i.e. characterizing. So, N.V. Gogol in his "Remarks for the Actors" described the complex image of Khlestakov as a man "without a tsar in his head." This is the remarkable property of phraseology - the generalizing role. The characterizing function of phraseology allows them to be used to characterize people both directly in the author's speech and in the speech of the characters themselves. [7]

Also studying the role of phraseological units in the speech of modern people, I conducted a survey in my group. The purpose of my survey was to find out whether university students know what phraseological units are, whether they understand the meaning of phraseological units, how often phraseological units are used in everyday speech.

So, during the survey, the following results were obtained: 18 people out of 20 respondents know what phraseological units are. Then the students were asked the task:

to give examples of phraseological units used by them in their speech, and it was revealed that out of 20 often and sometimes using phraseological units, two could not give their examples, and such as: "to hang noodles on their ears", "to lead by the nose", "to beat backbones", the least rare: "without hind legs", "the soul goes to the heels", "clap your ears", "get it on your nose", "wind it on your mustache", "beat the backbones" and "swallowed your tongue".[8]

I also found out that more than 15 students were able to correctly explain the meaning of all the proposed phraseological units. The greatest difficulty was caused by the phraseological units "headlong", "manna from heaven" and "Achilles' heel" (the latter two belong to the book style). Thus, I concluded that modern youth often uses phraseological units in their speech, which is why it can be called bright and expressive. [9]

In conclusion, I can say that based on the results of research, the following conclusions can be drawn: the role of phraseological units in the Russian language is great. Frequently they express the wise sayings of people who have become stable phrases. Each phraseology is a short expression of a long human thought.

Considering the origin and meaning of phraseological units in my work, I became convinced that the meaning of some phraseological units is directly related to their origin. Some types of phraseological units can be attributed to different classifications according to the degree of semantic unity, by style, as well as by origin. [10]

The relevance of the use of phraseological units in modern speech is indisputable. The whole history of the spiritual life of the people is reflected in the depths of the national language. That is why the best and even the only way to penetrate into the character of a people is to learn the peculiarities of its language. One of these features are phraseological units and phraseological turns. And also phraseological units adorn oral speech when communicating in society and shows the level of knowledge of a person's language.

References:

1. Marinova, E.V. A foreign-language word as a component of new phraseological units // Bulletin of the Nizhny Novgorod University. The series "Philology. Art criticism". - 2008. - No. 4. - pp. 246-251.
2. Maslova, V.A. Linguoculturology. - M., 2001.
3. Melerovich, A.M., Mokienko, V.M. Phraseological units in Russian speech. Dictionary. - M., 2001.
4. Mechkovskaya, N.B. Figurative conceptualization of graded-quantitative representations in Russian phraseology // Kognition, Sprachundphraseologische paromiologische Graduierung. HarrassowitzVerlag, Wiesbaden, 2005. - C. 58-153.
5. Mokienko, V.M. New Russian phraseology. - Opole, 2003.
6. Mokienko, V.M. Slavic phraseology. - M., 1989.
7. Nikitina, T.G. Youth slang: explanatory dictionary. - M., 2007.
8. Chernyak, V.D. Agnonyms in the lexicon of a linguistic personality as a source of communicative failures // Russian language today - M., 2003
9. Russian Phraseological Dictionary / Comp. L.A. Voynova et al.; edited by A.I. Molotkov. - M., 2006.
10. Phraseological dictionary of the Russian language for schoolchildren / Comp. L.A. Subbotina. - Yekaterinburg, 2007.
11. Russian Phraseological dictionary / Comp. A.N. Tikhonov. - M., 2007.
12. Kryukova G. A. On the question of the formation of a picture of the world among foreign students studying the Russian language // Bulletin of the Moscow University. Ser. 19. Linguistics and intercultural communication. - 2005. No. 1. pp. 136-140.